

SAR data processing on the edge: harnessing embedded GPUs and FPGAs to unlock onboard Earth monitoring

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Until nowadays, onboard payload data processing has been limited to passive payloads (i.e., optical images) only. However, active payloads, such as Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) systems, can provide high-quality images at a sub-meter resolution regardless of lighting and weather. The current paradigm for the exploitation of SAR data foresees the complete downlink of the collected raw signals and their processing in dedicated ground facilities. As a consequence, real-time Earth monitoring applications is today unfeasible with a SAR payload.

This work aims to establish the groundwork for a transformation in the SAR data processing domain. Our objective is to demonstrate the feasibility to run SAR processing algorithms on embedded hardware devices, such as NVIDIA Jetson GPU and Xilinx FPGA, with limited computational power. Our work represents a first step toward the next generation of SAR payload, opening up the opportunity to new concepts of operations.

1 Introduction

Among the technologies and sensor types used in space-based Earth Observation (EO) applications, SAR payloads play a crucial role: thanks to the active nature of their remote sensing principle, those sensors enable seamless Earth surface monitoring in all weather and illumination conditions. However, the exploitation of this enhanced quantity and quality of information is hindered by the higher degree of complexity that comes with SAR data utilization. In fact, raw SAR products are almost unintelligible to a human observer. The current paradigm delegates the SAR data processing completely to the ground segment, exploiting dedicated facilities to tackle the highly computationally intensive processing tasks. Considering the delays that come with downlink, processing, and dissemination bottlenecks, real-time monitoring and surveillance capabilities are hindered.

To unlock real-time space-based surveillance and monitoring intelligence, which is indeed an emerging need in the EO sector, enabling onboard data processing is a crucial capability for the next generation of EO satellites [1].

The aim of this work is to discuss and present our results about optimizing, deploying, and testing our SAR data processing workflow on embedded hardware devices, demonstrating the feasibility of running these processes onboard the next generation of SAR missions.

2 Onboard SAR data processing workflow

As discussed in Section 1, the main goal of this work is to revolutionise the current SAR processing paradigm, equipping the spacecraft with SAR data processing capabilities and enabling quasi-real time onboard maritime monitoring. To achieve this, we propose a Machine Learning-based approach that allows to enable onboard intelligence in SAR missions.

Our solution is a hybrid architecture that incorporates both image formation and detection steps that should guarantee a fine localization level, as well as a raw processing, in charge of providing a coarse localization level and speed up the entire processing chain. Therefore, the proposed architecture is composed by three main algorithmic blocks:

- **Scene classification (SC):** it takes as input the raw acquisition and leverages a Deep Learning (DL) network to perform patch-wise binary classification, in order to identify possible regions of interest (ROIs) characterized by the presence of ships. ROIs are regions labelled in the raw products, as they are characterized by the presence of one or more ships echoes.

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- **Focusing (FOC):** it takes as input the raw acquisition and performs Deep Learning-based SAR image formation, giving as output a coarse Level-1 Single-Look Complex (SLC) product. Its architecture comprised a two-steps approach: Fast-Fourier-Transform-based (FFT) range processing and Deep Learning-based azimuth processing [2].
- **Ship detection (SD):** it takes as input the coarse SLC product and performs patch-wise Deep Learning-based ship detection, providing localization bounding boxes.

3 Hardware selection

Among the different embedded devices of interest for the Space industry, NVIDIA Jetson Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) [3] and Xilinx Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) [4] have been selected to perform a benchmarking. This allows to perform a comprehensive analysis between the most two common hardware families that are used to accelerate machine learning-based algorithms.

After a trade-off of these two device families, we chose the NVIDIA Jetson GPU Xavier and Orin, while for the FPGAs, we identified the Xilinx UltraScale+ ZCU104 and Xilinx Versal.

(a) NVIDIA Jetson Xavier NX

(b) Xilinx Versal AI Core series VCK190

Figure 1: Hardware devices.

The choice of these devices also comes from the fact that they have already been used for space missions or will be used in future launches. FPGAs have

demonstrated significant utility in space missions because of tolerance to radiation while maintaining low power consumption. The Xilinx UltraScale+ MPSoC is widely used and thus already demonstrated in low Earth orbit (LEO) and Geostationary orbit (GEO) orbits. The Xilinx Versal family is under development for upcoming missions and AMD will release space-grade versions soon. Radiation tests have already been carried out and because of the high computational capabilities, they can bring many benefits in applications that require high throughput such as on-board SAR data processing. GPUs, on the other hand, provide excellent performance, can be considered as general-purpose devices and are easy to program. Despite they have not yet reached the space-grade qualification, Nvidia Jetson GPUs are characterized by a high TRL and are also already capable of operating in orbit. The Jetson Xavier NX has already been deployed in LEO and the Jetson Orin is under development for space missions.

4 Embedded SW optimisation

Embedded software (SW) optimisation foresees different procedures for the GPU and FPGA devices.

Concerning the GPUs, the models are accelerated with TensorRT, an inference optimization and runtime library developed by NVIDIA. In addition, to further speed up inference and optimize the computational efficiency, the numerical precision of the models has been reduced from 32 to 16 bits. Regarding FPGAs, Vitis AI has been employed. This is a development platform by AMD, designed for accelerating and deploying models on AMD device. It offers a unified software stack, enabling efficient integration, optimization, and deployment of AI models also onto Xilinx FPGA.

For FPGAs, quantization is even more important than for GPUs. In fact, these hardware devices can only accelerate inference on numerical integer representations; thus, models have been converted from 32-bit floating point representations to 8-bit integers.

The following tables provides an overview of the preliminary performance in terms of FPS, for the different models across the different hardware (HW) devices.

5 Deployment results

To demonstrate the performance achieved by the proposed solution, we consider the Sentinel-1 (S-1) satellite, a European Space Agency (ESA) mission in the context of EU Copernicus Earth Observation program

Table 1: ML/DL models performance (FPS) after optimization and deployment.

	SC	FOC	SD
NVIDIA Jetson Xavier @10W	82	22	79
NVIDIA Jetson Xavier @20W	110	45	144
NVIDIA Jetson Orin @15W	126	38	134
NVIDIA Jetson Orin @30W	272	76	245
Xilinx UltraScale+ ZCU104	28	6	39
Xilinx Versal	254	59	222

Note: @W stands for power consumption setting expressed in Watt (W).

[5]. S-1 satellites are equipped with a C-band SAR payload that can operate in four acquisition modes, namely Stripmap (SM), Interferometric Wide Swath (IW), Extra Wide Swath (EW), and Wave (WV). SM and IW modes have been selected to assess the performance of the proposed solution but, for the sake of clarity and brevity, this section previews the results obtained on the SM products.

A customized dataset has been generated to train and test each algorithmic component. The focusing dataset consists of triplets of raw, range compressed, and single-look complex (SLC) products obtained by applying Range Doppler Algorithm (RDA) on raw products retrieved from [6]. Subsequently, the SLC products are manually annotated with bounding boxes for ship detection. Finally, those labels are transposed back to the raw data level to generate a mask indicating target ROIs in the raw product. An example of the different products and annotations derived is displayed in Figure 2.

More than 20 S-1 products have been downloaded to construct the dataset needed for training and testing the data-driven algorithmic workflow. Naturally, each block needs a tailored dataset preparation pipeline in terms of data pre-processing (e.g., tiling, scaling).

Once the different blocks have been properly trained, they are optimized and deployed on the hardware devices selected in Section 3. This process aims at demonstrating the feasibility of running the pipeline in a limited computational power scenario, and to evaluate the results in terms of performance metrics and inference times.

Performance results related to scene classification and ship detection building blocks are summarized in Table 2. The main focus of the quantitative performance assessment has been devoted to these two algorithmic blocks, as the focusing algorithm is designed solely to act as a pre-processing step to enable further processing and onboard tasks. However, apart from qualitative assessment and visual inspection, a loss in resolution has been measured on DL-focused

Figure 2: S1 dataset example for maritime monitoring.

products by computing the Impulse Response Function (IRF), resulting approximately in a factor of 2.

Table 2: Performance results.

	Precision	Recall	F1
Scene classification	0.60	0.68	0.64
Ship detection	0.79	0.58	0.67

Profiling results are extracted from the full processing of a Stripmap acquisition approximately of size 20.000x2000 (range x azimuth); they are broken down for the three different building blocks (Focusing - FOC, Scene Classification - SC, Ship Detection - SD) and reported in Table 3.

Table 3: Profiling results.

	SC [s]	FOC [s]	SD [s]
NVIDIA Jetson Xavier @10W	1.77	26.03	2.33
NVIDIA Jetson Xavier @20W	1.32	14.21	1.45
NVIDIA Jetson Orin @15W	1.15	25.19	2.07
NVIDIA Jetson Orin @30W	0.53	10.40	0.96
Xilinx UltraScale+ ZCU104	5.53	93.96	6.59
Xilinx Versal	0.61	23.99	2.02

Optimization and testing have also been performed on the traditional RDA for focusing, which has been tested on the NVIDIA devices allowing a first comparison of the overall gain in inference time. The tests resulted in a total execution time of 34.75 seconds on NVIDIA Jetson Xavier @20W and 21.72 seconds

on NVIDIA Jetson Orin @30W. As a result, our approach demonstrates an improvement between 50% and 60%.

An important consideration is related to the higher percentage of time required to the focusing algorithm on the Versal device when compared to the Jetson ones. This discrepancy is due to the higher time take by the FFT range compression step and it can be attributed to a suboptimal optimization effort done on Versal, where the main goal was to achieve the full deployment and having the implementation up and running. Our implementation of the range compression for Xilinx devices is in fact the simplest, whereby only the individual FFTs are processed in the programmable logic of the FPGA. In fact, there exists ample opportunity to decrease the processing time for range compression on Versal, such as exploring batch processing, optimizing the memory accesses to minimize data movements and delegate the execution to AI engines to speed up the FFT execution. Overall, the processing time breakdown (both for the RDA and DL implementation) on the various devices and power settings is provided in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Processing time breakdown.

6 Conclusions

This research effort represents a breakthrough in onboard processing for SAR missions. By combining automation workflows with Deep Learning models, the proposed architecture overcomes current limitations in deploying onboard data processing algorithms mainly because of limited processing power, paving the way for near real-time remote sensing applications. Additionally, its flexible design allows for adaptation to various onboard Earth observation tasks that needs access to content-rich SAR data.

Naturally, this work leaves ample room for improvements in various directions. The main ones are identified as:

- **Functional improvements:** first of all, there is the need of assessing the generalization capabilities of the algorithms across different SAR sensors and operative modes. Moreover, the use cases pool shall be extended with additional remote sensing applications that largely benefits from the usage of SAR data (e.g., oil spill detection, flood monitoring).
- **Performance improvements:** performance metrics shall be improved for the identified use cases. Both a high rate of false positives and false negatives can dramatically impact onboard monitoring applications in terms of resources utilization and response latency.
- **Deployment improvements:** the major obstacle to fully unleash the computational performance throughout this work has been the sub-optimal deployment on FPGAs. In future works, there is the need of improving this activity to exploit their capabilities and processing power. Moreover, for what concerns the algorithms deployment on the target HW, a next step is related to the definition of the set of HW/SW requirements (taking into account resources, I/O interfaces) required to run the proposed solution onboard.

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